

Business Domain Modelling Using an Integrated Framework

Mohammed Salahat, Steve Wade

Abstract—This paper presents an application of a “Systematic Soft Domain Driven Design Framework” as a soft systems approach to domain-driven design of information systems development. The framework use SSM as a guiding methodology within which we have embedded a sequence of design tasks based on the UML leading to the implementation of a software system using the Naked Objects framework. This framework have been used in action research projects that have involved the investigation and modelling of business processes using object-oriented domain models and the implementation of software systems based on those domain models. Within this framework, Soft Systems Methodology (SSM) is used as a guiding methodology to explore the problem situation and to develop the domain model using UML for the given business domain. The framework is proposed and evaluated in our previous works, and a real case study “Information Retrieval System for academic research” is used, in this paper, to show further practice and evaluation of the framework in different business domain. We argue that there are advantages from combining and using techniques from different methodologies in this way for business domain modelling. The framework is overviewed and justified as multimethodology using Mingers multimethodology ideas.

Keywords—SSM, UML, domain-driven design, soft domain-driven design, naked objects, soft language, information retrieval, multimethodology.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE business domain for any organization accommodates the organization business process that must be well defined and modelled for the implementation. Business domain comprises the business process can be defined as ‘the transformation of something from one state to another state through partially coordinated agents, with the purpose of achieving certain goals that are derived from the responsibility of the process owner’ [16].

To support the business domain, good information systems software used to support the organization work by handling the internal business process and control all aspects affecting the execution of the process. The business process must be supported with good business process modeling (domain modeling) and implementation techniques that can analyze, model, and implement the business process in a professional way to achieve the organizational goals [18].

The failure of software support systems has been well

Mohammed Salahat is a Lecturer in Ajman University of Science and Technology in UAE and a part-time-PhD student in the School of Computing and Engineering, University of Huddersfield, UK (e-mail: m.salahat@ajman.ac.ae, u0423855@hud.ac.uk).

Steve Wade is a senior Lecturer in the Informatics department, School of Computing and Engineering, University of Huddersfield (e-mail: s.j.wade@hud.ac.uk)

documented over the years, and many of these failures have been attributed to poor business process modelling [1]. One of the main reasons for information systems failure is a tendency to concentrate on the technical aspects of design rather than understanding the business needs [2]. There is a need for a systematic approach for capturing the information required by business processes [1]. This suggests a need to bridge the gap between business process modelling, information systems modelling, and implementation. The bridging framework may be will enhance the development of proper information systems and the IS development process. It is named SDDD (Soft Domain-Driven Design) and it aims to investigate, analyze and model a business domain so that we can implement it as a software support system [4], [5], [21]-[24]. SDDD is a multimethodology systemic framework consisting of four phases with guiding procedures to steer the developer between the various compromises that need to be made throughout the development process. The paper will be presented as follows:

Section II reviews related work. Section III briefed the research methodology used. Section IV is introduced the framework as a multimethodology approach. Section V is a brief description of a practical case study “An information retrieval system for academic research” in which the method has been applied. Section VI presents a reflection on the framework and the learning process of applying it. Section VII is conclusion and future works.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Domain Driven Modelling (DDM)

The business domain for any organization accommodates the organization business process that must be well defined and modelled for the implementation. Business domain comprises the business process that can be defined as ‘the transformation of something from one state to another state through partially coordinated agents, with the purpose of achieving certain goals that are derived from the responsibility of the process owner’ [16]. There are many definitions of “business process”, and the most of these definitions are based on the idea of a business process as a deterministic system that receives inputs and transforms into outputs following a series of activities. For example [17] defines business processes as “‘structured sets of activities designed to produce a specified output for a particular customer or market’”. Business processes are similar in different business domains running the same industry of business. To support the business domain, good information systems software is used to support the organization work by handling the internal business process and controlling all aspects affecting the execution of the process. The business

process must be supported with good business process modeling (domain modeling) and implementation techniques that can analyze, model, and implement the business process in a professional way to achieve the organizational goals [18].

B. Domain-Driven Design

Domain-Driven Design can be used to model the business process as a business domain model [6]. A Ubiquitous Language (UL) is generated first as a communication tool between different stakeholders and the domain model will be generated and implemented based on UL. UML diagrams are sufficient tools for requirement modelling to support business process modelling in an object-oriented domain model [19]. When it comes to implementing the system we have made use of the DDD implementation pattern (i.e. Naked Objects or True View) to reflect the system interface directly from the domain model. Naked Objects [20] and True View Domain Modeler are used for exploring Business Domains and creating rapid prototypes using Domain Driven Design. It helps you to work with your Domain Experts to understand business entities, relationships and the business' ubiquitous language and to write classes using .NET and the Naked Objects or True View framework.

C. Soft Domain Driven Design

Soft Domain Driven Design [21] is an approach that seeks to model the system processes as a domain model and develop a software support system based on it. In DDD Ubiquitous Language was used to create the domain model by the developers and domain experts [6] and to facilitate the communication between different stakeholders. UML, as a part of SDDD, defines a number of diagrams that can be used to model the business process [7] but lacks the ability to explore the soft issues related to the problematic situation which can be handled using Soft System Methodology. SSM is an established means of problem solving that focuses on the development of idealized models of relevant systems that can then be compared with real world counterparts [8]-[10]. SSM is used in SDDD to model the business domain using rich pictures, root definition, and conceptual model. In our previous work [21], we have adapted the idea of a Ubiquitous Language into a "Soft Language" which incorporates certain artifacts of a SSM analysis into the model. The first step of the SDDD approach is to develop a 'Soft Language' as result of the application of Soft System Methodology. This language is an a compliment of the Ubiquitous Language described in Domain-Driven Design [6] which consists of different concepts, diagrams, and documents to facilitate the communications between the developers and domain experts. Some researchers have explored the relationship between SSM and object oriented analysis and design techniques in general [11] but less has been written about the application of these techniques in the context of the UML. An object-oriented domain model can be extracted from this Soft Language through a transition process from SSM Conceptual Model to UML Use Cases. We argue here that SSM helps the developer to gain a deep understanding of different stakeholders' perspectives which

will need to be represented in the Soft Language. In this paper we argue that this transition supported the students understanding of modeling the business domain and implementing the software support system based on that.

As described in our previous work [21] SDDD framework guides the developer into creating a "Soft Language" which consists of the output of the SSM stage to deal with the soft aspects which are not handled explicitly by Domain Driven Design. The SSM Conceptual Primary task Model (CPTM) is used to map human activity to a UML use-case model using a new elaboration technique. Use-cases, as abstractions of business activities, are used to model the business process in a domain model using UML diagrams and based on the philosophy of DDD which employs the idea of "Knowledge Crunching" during the different stages. To the best of our knowledge, this combination has not been applied in an intervention before, and an evaluation in teaching context and the application in business projects will be a contribution to this domain of research and software development.

D. Other Related Works

Previous works consider the SSM conceptual model as a focal point for linking SSM and UML by mapping the activities of an SSM conceptual model into UML use-cases [12], [13]. Recent examples of this approach can be found in SWfM [7] and our previous works [4], [5], [21]. Other researchers have made use of various extensions to the UML. For example [3] employed a systemic framework combining SSM and UML extensions proposed by [14] to model the business process of a manufacturing factory. Their framework is based on Mingers Multimethodology ideas [15] but does not encompass the software implementation phase of development.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research, as part of on-going research work, aims to answer the following research question:

How to Model and Implement the Business Domain Processes into a Domain-Driven Design System?

Both authors are involved in teaching in their Universities. This encouraged us to use the approach of Action Research since we are actors and part of any system in the education environment and for us it is the domain to apply any research. By teaching systems modelling and design for many years by both authors, we found from teaching and the literature review that many software systems failed and the reason of failures because of the tendency to focus more on the technical aspects rather than the Business Domain Processes modeling [1]. The majority of software development methodologies initiated from the software engineering science and not given sufficient attention to the business processes modeling for any given business domain. Involving the business experts with the technical people to investigate and model any domain needs a methodology or framework that can be used by different stockholders and facilitate the communication between them. Among this Domain Driven Design is dominant but still the communication depends on the technical system concepts

which may be a problem for the business expert to understand. Soft System Methodology is well-established and known as an approach to explore problematic situation. Based on that, this ongoing research suggested the combination between SSM, UML as a modeling language, and an implementation pattern satisfied the philosophy of Domain-Driven Design as a dominant approach among others. The new approach is proposed and published in our previous work [21] and further evaluation from the development perspective taken place in this paper. To answer the above research question and to apply the research as it's designed, the following methodology followed:

1. Review the current situation of business domain processes modelling through teaching and literature review. A comparison between different approaches done based on that.
2. Formulate and propose a multimethodology framework considering soft and hard business domain aspects.
3. Evaluate the framework through different practical case studies as an undergraduate and Msc projects (Peer-Tutoring System, University Students Associations System, and Information Retrieval system).
4. Reflect on the implementation and record learning from the methodology application in order to guide further applications.
5. Reflect on the framework as an approach of business domain modelling and implementation.

IV. THE SDDD FRAMEWORK

The SDDD framework [21] is briefed here to relate it with the evaluation in order to facilitate the understanding process of the reader. SDDD was developed into an action research intervention based on research of multimethodology, which justifies combining methods for the same business intervention [15]. It is a multi-method framework which intended to guide the developer through an investigation of a problematic situation. The purpose here is to insure that a comprehensive understanding is achieved in order to facilitate the modelling and implementation of the domain-driven business processes as a software support system. The modelling will produce an object-oriented domain-driven model as the bases of developing the software support system. As mentioned in the previous work [21], the framework was been developed through a series of "action research" case studies. Accordingly our case studies have involved development projects within our own school. In this paper, an *Information Retrieval System for academic research researchers* investigated as an MSc Project to evaluate the SDDD applicability in modelling the business domain processes into object-oriented domain model. The researchers are part of the school and they are participating in the daily activities related to the case studies. They supervised the students and guided them to the final stage of the projects and teaching courses related to business domain modelling and implementation.

The SDDDF Framework (Fig. 1) is focused on modelling and implementation of the domain-driven business process as a software support system. SSM is used as a guiding and

learning methodology with techniques including UML and implementation pattern (Naked Object or True View) embedded within it. The DDD philosophy is adapted to generate a "Soft Language" (SL) as a compliment of "Ubiquitous Language" (UL) and it used as an input to the next stages. The implementation pattern is used after the generation of the final refined change report which is an input to the implementation process.

Fig. 1 The SDDDF Model

Fig. 2 The conception of SDDDF

Using [15] generic model which discussed in [21], the SDDD framework consists of four phases and each phase consists of a group of activities. The framework satisfies the generic process of conducting an action research in the

business intervention. SDDD represented in Fig. 1; Fig. 2 represents the conceptualization of the framework; and Fig. 3 represents the logical processes embedded in it. For more details about these phases refer to [21], [22].

V. THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION RETRIEVAL SYSTEM USING SDDD FRAMEWORK

Since we have been engaged in an information systems development project using SSM and UML techniques within an agile framework to make recommendations about the development of an intranet for the academic school in which we are employed. At the beginning of the project the department had an operational intranet but this was not widely used. An information system strategy was initiated to investigate ways in which the intranet could be developed to support the university mission and departmental goals. Initially we used use cases as the primary fact-gathering technique but certain limitations in this approach led us to a more thorough SSM-based analysis of the situation. We argue that the techniques of SSM can help the developer to identify a richer set of use cases than would otherwise be possible but developers with a full use case model still have many challenges ahead of them. We are interested in object oriented design and the view that all business behavior identified in the use case model should be encapsulated as methods on domain objects. Thus, a Student object should not just be a collection of data about the Student; it should encapsulate all the behaviors that we need to apply to a student. In Domain-Driven Design these are often referred to as 'behaviorally-rich' domain objects. A number of software systems required supporting the department and one of these is Information Retrieval System for academic research researchers. The information retrieval system we proposed to design is that which provides academics the necessary facilities to aid in the precise and relevant information retrieval (IR) from databases across the internet. IR can be undertaken by the academics by using several different navigation paths returning the same significant data retrieval. The information retrieval system aims to provide academic students and staff to submit search criteria utilizing various options including general search, advanced searching, and Tag based operations. Furthermore students and staff can add tags to documents which can be used as another means of document navigation as well as information retrieval. The effectiveness and efficiency of this system is entirely dependent on the financial constraints of the Universities subscriptions and the ability of the academics to provide effective tagging.

A. Pre-SSM Phase

1. The Problem Identification

It is mentioned in the previous work [21] that the Department of Informatics in the School of Computing and Engineering at the University of Huddersfield in UK needs to investigate and develop certain systems to support the staff and students. In previous publications some of these applications investigated using SDDDF and this one will investigate the Information Retrieval System requested by the staff and

students. As an action researcher, we conducted the interviews in an informal way and done face to face so that the participants will be feeling comfortable during the interview as they can see who is interviewing them hence also giving their ideas and suggestions comfortably. With some ideas, participants were better explained by face to face interviews for example expressions which may not be fully explained in writing or over the phone. These actions were being noted throughout the interviews and appreciated unlike over the phone that these cannot be appreciated.

Fig. 3 SSSDF logic Pre-SSM Phase

The interviews were targeted to collect the following information:

- What is the current system offering? (Lecturers & students).
- How far the text box can go in supporting them with their works in classroom hours? (Lecturers)
- What do they think of IRS? (both)
- How can IRS support them to do their assignments and projects? (students)
- Would they need more information to support on the work to increase their lecturing skills? (Lecturers).

2. Stakeholders Determination

The stakeholders defined in this case are the people that will be using the system, and who will benefit from it. The stakeholders of the required IRS system were determined to be students, academic staff, and department management. The stakeholders have different expectations of the system. The different stakeholders of this system expected that they can

achieve the following from using it:

- Support them to search and retrieve latest information
- Minimize the time required for looking of extra information resources

B. SSM-Phase

1. Investigating the Problem Situation Using a Rich Picture

A rich picture is a drawing that graphically illustrates the issues expressed by people, processes involved in the transformation, people involved with or affected by the change (stakeholders), working climate, conflicts and structures within the change process [25].

In order to develop a rich picture of the situation under study, a number of information sources were used to capture views of Information Retrieval System from the perspective of the management the school of computing and engineering, lecturers, and students. Interviews with the school administration and groups of students were conducted to understand the problematic situation of getting the proper information required to deliver different courses and set out suggestions to solve the problems. Fig. 4 represents the Rich Picture of IRS.

Fig. 4 IRS Rich Picture

2. Modelling the Relevant System Using SSM (Root Definition & Conceptual Model)

Modelling the system using Root Definition is described by [9] as a movement from the real world to systems thinking about the real world. Reference [25] mentioned that during root definition stage, points of views from the different stakeholders are drawn out from the rich picture and have them in a structured development process. Root Definition (RD) of the IRS is as follows:

“The information retrieval system aims to provide academic students and staff to submit search criteria utilizing various options including general search, advanced searching, and Tag based operations. Furthermore students and staff can add tags to documents which can be used as another means of document navigation as well as information retrieval. The effectiveness and efficiency of this system is entirely dependent on the financial constraints of the Universities

subscriptions and the ability of the academics to provide effective tagging”.

Root definition has been used to extract the conceptual model which represents the different stakeholder views. So the conceptual model describes activities that might take place if the relevant root definition was to be an accurate representation of the work of a system. The following Conceptual Model of IRS (Fig. 5) represents the different stakeholders’ views, the actions that must be taken based on their views, and also meeting their particular cultural, political and social requirements of the system. All of these issues are expressed in the rich picture and modelled using the conceptual model.

Rich picture, root definition, and conceptual models represent the output of the SSM phase, and it’s called “Soft Language”.

Fig. 5 The Conceptual Model of IRS

C. Post I-SSM Phase: Moving from Soft Language (SSM Phase) to Domain Model

Domain Model will be represented using UML. Domain modeling starts with the conversion from the Conceptual Model into Use Cases and Use Case modeling. The extracted

Use cases will be used to develop UML Sequence Diagram, Class diagram, and Activity Diagrams development. The next subsection 1 will show the conversion from CM to Use Cases.

1. Transition from SSM Conceptual Model to UML Use Cases

The conversion process is presented in Fig. 9. Any activity required software support will be selected as a use case. The stage of moving from an SSM conceptual model to a use cases 1 is not as straightforward as this high-level discussion would suggest. In thinking this through we have been pushed towards making a clear distinction between stakeholder goals, business activities and use cases. Fig. 6 shows the relationship between these key abstractions.

Fig. 6 Transition from SSM to use case diagram

Using the above conversion algorithm, the conceptual models presented above converted into different use case. The following Use Case diagram (Fig. 7) presented as a result of the conversion process. This figure show the identified use cases and actors within the search function of the system. The 2 actors are the academics and the collection of databases. It can be clearly seen that the actor can do 2 types of search; query based and tag based. Query search can be further split up into its types of search, these are: general search and advanced search. The Boolean search is incorporated into the advanced search. The actor can type words into the tag search bar and these will be checked against the current “Doc Tag Index” to see if it matches. This is equivalent of having auto suggestive tags matching the partial string the actor is inputting. The actor can also click on existing tags in the cloud and these will automatically bring up the list of documents attached to that tag.

These use cases described using use case proforma which is a template to show the logic embedded in each use case. Fig. 8 shows a sample of use case proforma to represent the general search process.

2. Generate the Activity Diagrams

Fig. 9 shows the activity diagram of the search functionality in the information retrieval system. The actors can search in various ways: general search, advanced search and tag based search. The general search is just a basic keyword search, the advanced search uses Boolean operation (AND mainly) in having more than one type of search criteria, i.e. searching for an Author AND Publication Year. Finally tag based searching firstly allows the actor to search through already processed tags attached to documents and they are used in auto completion

when typing in the tag field.

Fig. 7 The use case diagram of IRS

3. Generate Class Diagram

A class diagram is a representation of a basic structure of a system, it shows what classes will be present in the system, how the classes are going to link between themselves and how many links to one class there would be from another. It's a presentation of the system to more detail. Each use case presented using textual template, activity diagram, sequence diagram, and all use cases are combined in a use case diagram. The next step in the process is to take the business logic identified in the use cases and associate it with classes in a class diagram. We have followed the guideline that all important business logic must be implemented in classes in the domain model. Class diagram is the major part of the Domain Model that can be used to generate the programming code through the implementation pattern. Class diagram of RIS is presented in Fig. 10.

4. Change Report Generation and Refinement

As shown in the framework (SDDD), there is a draw back to the previous stages to refine what's done during Pre-SSM, SSM, and Post1-SSM. This refinement is essential to be sure that the exact changes required already modelled well as a domain model. As a guiding methodology, SSM focus on the generation of the required change report as a result to be recommended for the management actions [8]-[10]. So, before leaving this stage, Domain model supposed to be refined and ready for implementation.

Use Case Number: 3	Use Case Name: Tag based search
Overview: This use case will be executed daily and concurrently by hundreds of actors a day. This use case allows the actors to perform searches by tags inputted. An auto suggestive tag function will match up the string the actor is inputting in real time.	
Actors: Academics.	
Frequency of execution: This use case will be run daily.	
Scalability This process will have several instances running at one time.	
Criticality: This use case is extremely critical again for this type of search. With this functionality down it may affect other critical systems for the tag cloud functionality.	
Primary Path: 1) Actor decides to do a tag search 2) Actor begins to enter tag into the text field. 3) Auto suggestive tagging searches tag index for matching tag. 4) Suggested tag matches actor input, 5) Actor clicks on tag, 6) Doc Tag Index is checked to gather all documents attached to the queried tag. 7) The list of documents are displayed to the actor and ready to view.	
Use Cases related to Primary Path: Document Index Search. This is because as the actor enters the tag, it automatically tries to match it up with an entry in the Doc Tag database.	
Alternatives: 4.1 – If no tags are matched then the auto suggestive tagger will simply display “No tags found” and allows the actor to perform another tag search or a different search type.	
Use Cases related to Alternatives: None	
Exceptions: None	
Use Cases related to Exceptions: None	

Fig. 8 Use case proforma of general search

D. Post2-SSM Phase: Software Implementation

SDDD framework considered the domain model as the base to extract the programming code using the implementation pattern. Naked objects [20] and True view are recommended as implementation patterns. The purpose of this paper is to show the business modelling part and the implementation is still going on and not presented here.

VI. REFLECTIONS ON THE FRAMEWORK

Our work in applying the framework to a series of real-world development projects has focused our attention on a number of issues that we had not considered at the outset.

Some of these present difficulties for the further development of the framework which present opportunities for further research. Some of these will be briefly discussed in this section.

A. Role of Re-Use and Design Patterns in Domain Modelling

Our approach tries to preserve as much “soft” information as possible in the evolving domain models. Inevitably some of this information is lost as we move from approaches that try to model what “people” are doing (including activities that do not require software support) through to program code. At present our framework leads to development of a bespoke software system based on a rich object-oriented domain model. In practice many software developers make use of reusable software components or wish to design software with an eye to future reuse. There is clearly a tension between our emphasis on a bespoke solution and the software developers’ objective of developing generic, reusable software solutions.

B. Representation of Implicit Information in the Domain Model

The conceptual models in SSM do not have rigorous syntax. We have discovered that when developing the conceptual models people often include information in, for example, the sequence of activities or the knowledge required to carry out certain activities which is lost when we move into the use case and object models. We are attempting to develop clear guidelines for identifying this type of information and what should be done about it. One possibility is that we develop our own version of conceptual models that do include a more prescriptive notation.

C. Ambiguity in the Definition of “Business Process”

One of the issues that we have confronted is the lack of consensus about precisely what can be defined as a business process and what cannot. SSM has a number of techniques for capturing multiple stakeholder perspectives on what the key business processes are and how they should be monitored. We want to preserve these multiple perspectives for as long as possible into the development process. At present we take the Consensus Primary Task Model produced in SSM to be an objective description of what is required but we have found that it is often difficult to gain consensus in developing this model and then to preserve that consensus as we move on.

Fig. 9 Activity Diagram

Fig. 10 The Class Diagram of RIS System

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The work done in this paper reviewed and highlighted the need for a multimethodology framework that can handle both soft and hard issues of domain business process modelling and implementation as a software support system. The new proposed framework is developed based on the idea of Domain-Driven Design (DDD) and Soft Systems Methodology (SSM). We have added a “soft” perspective on DDD to form “Soft Domain-Driven Design”. The approach is described as a systemic framework for domain business process modelling and implementation. The framework is proposed and justified as a multimethodology framework, incorporating guiding steps through various key stages in the development process. The framework is being evaluated and further developed in an action research program. We briefly provided the example of “Information Retrieval System” (RIS) case study to show how the proposed framework can be applied to a real problem situation. More evaluations of the framework have been done through the development of other projects within the University of Huddersfield. These projects are “Combined Studies Program Development System”, “Peer-Tutoring System”, and “Placement Unit Management System. All evaluation results show the applicability of the framework as a domain modelling and implementation approach for ISD projects. Also pedagogical evaluations show the applicability of the framework as a teaching approach.

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